
Reviewing Three-Language Formula in Language Pedagogy

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Abstract

Language is sometimes used to refer to codes, ciphers, signs, and symbols etc. Using a language may be a process of encoding and decoding information. Learning a language is a sort of cognitive ability to use the symbols and articulate in a communicative manner. We acquire language initially through interaction then develop or construct it as per time, place, and requirement. The objective of this review article is to analyze the significance of three language formula for the learners of English.

Keywords: Learning Language, vocabulary, grammar, semantics

Since the beginning of the existence, human being has learned the art to communicate with one another. Today, English is one of the popular languages of the globe. Due to globalization, the knowledge of English has become a must. Widely used language for communication. It has the most extensive and expressive vocabulary as well. According to three language formulae first language is Regional language, second is National language and third is International Language. English has become the necessity and unconditioned requirement for the globe. It has been observed that before entering the mainstream of Medical Education, Engineering, Business Management etc., we complete our school education with the impression of mother tongue and the dominant regional tongue as well.

According to Palmer (1978), communicative language teaching lays emphasis on semantic aspects of language. Language is essentially a system of meaning potential. The socio-linguistic works of both Holliday and Hymes are important to for imparting English Language through communicative approach. They have opined that the social context, grammar and meaning are interrelated. Das (1974) opines that the major distinctive features of the communicative approach as contrasted with the audio-lingual method are (a)

Meaning is paramount (b) Dialogues, if used, center around communicative functions and are not normally memorized,(c) Conceptualization is a basic premise (d) Language learning is learning to communicate,(e) Effective communication is sought, (f)Drilling may occur, but peripherally,(g)Comprehensible pronunciation is sought (h) Any device, which helps the learners, is accepted varying according to their age, interest etc.(i)Attempts to communicate may be encouraged from the very beginning. Judicious use of native language is accepted where feasible (j) Translation may be used where students need or likely to get benefit from it, (k) Reading and writing can start from the first day, if desired,(l) Communicative competence is the desired goal (i.e. the ability to use the linguistic system effectively and appropriately) (m) Linguistic variation is a central concept in materials and methodology (n) Sequencing is determined by any consideration of content, function, or meaning which maintains interest (o)Teachers help learners to motivate them to work with the language,(p) Language is created by the individual after thorough trial and error method,(q) Fluency and acceptable language is the primary goal accuracy is judged not in the abstract but in context,(r) Students are expected to interact with other people either in the flesh through pair and group work, or in their writings. (s) Intrinsic motivation will spring from an interest in what is being communicated by the language

Our everyday would not be possible without interaction and communication. All of us make use of different languages for communicative purpose. We express our desires, concerns, and feedback through a language itself. The selection of words, tone and pitch is subject to the place, position, and audience as well. Thus, we assume that proper communication skill is the backbone of our society. An expression and two forms, i.e., written and spoken. A written form uses a certain symbol with correct grammar whereas the spoken part relates to the way one articulates.

The outcome of our expression through speaking skill is determined by the context, tone, and pitch. Our body language also plays a vital role in t whereas the written form is subject to coherence and flow of thought. However, we need to keep the audience as well in mind before expressing something. Therefore, the association between these two forms of expression is a bit intricate. It is an irony to see that today's educational planning is made and monitored by unrealistic personnel who do not meet any eligibility criteria or prerequisite of becoming decision makers on English issues (Jha, 2014). The role of a trainer is important for imparting both the forms of expression in a balanced manner.

Krashen &Terrell (1983) similarly contended that specific education helps learners make sense of words in input utterances and draws their interest to language. In their opinion, when learners understand little about the target language, it is very difficult for them to understand non-salient grammatical, meaning-forming relationships, such as participles and inflections. Mohammed (1993), citing Gass (1991), stated that "Explicit grammar teaching makes learners aware of the discrepancies between what they themselves have constructed for their second language and the system which becomes apparent to them for the target language data they are confronted with. In other words, it acts as a selective attention device", "

Let us try to analyze inductive and deductive approaches to imparting English Language. Some academicians consider that an inductive approach might only be effective for teaching relatively simple grammatical patterns. They think that some complicated rules are not easy for learners to master intuitively. The inductive approach refers to the technique of introducing language framework containing the focus rules where students can encourage such rules through the context and real-life examples.

Although some academicians from inductive approaches assume that it is not easy for weak students, Shaffer (1989) argued that the inductive approach is valuable for all levels of students, but especially for weak students. Shaffer's study (1989) not only confirmed the finding of the cognitive psychologist Bruner (1961) that "Students do better when having to discover underlying patterns themselves rather than being told about them, but also provided evidence that the inductive approach can be used to teach difficult structures.

The deductive approach has accepted much criticism from the perspective of cognitive psychology, which stresses that learners should actively contribute to their own learning. Piaget (1974) claimed that learners need to be involved in the interaction between their innate structures of the mind and the outside learning environment. In his opinion when learners find out underlying patterns for themselves, the learned knowledge lasts longer in human memory. Garrett & James (1991) criticized that although the deductive approach may offer explanations of linguistic rules, it does not help students connect the form with the meaning in their cognitive mechanism. For them, "The separation of form and meaning is not only impossible in terms of all that we know about the nature of language knowledge and students express their own meaning in the language use, but also counter-productive in terms of our philosophical goal of helping appropriate forms of the target language."

Thus, the notion that linguistics might be useful in studying the significance of three formulae languages and other cultural phenomena. There are based on social and cultural phenomenon, symbols and signs, internal and external learning factors. The mother tongue, national language and the International language can be acquired to classrooms and beyond.

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